

ORGANIZATION AND PRINCIPLES OF MARKETING SERVICE IN THE CONDITIONS OF MODERNIZATION OF THE COUNTRY

Musayeva Shoirazimovna,

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7422491>

Abstract. *In this article, the possibilities of production and sale of the enterprise, their socio-economic, technical and technological aspects, determination of norms of use of labor resources, study of competitiveness of goods produced by various enterprises, as well as organization of rational sale of their goods are considered.*

Keywords: *Enterprise, market, need, labor, resource, normative, commodity, sale.*

ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ И ПРИНЦИПЫ МАРКЕТИНГОВОЙ СЛУЖБЫ В УСЛОВИЯХ МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ СТРАНЫ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассмотрены возможности производства и реализации предприятия, их социально-экономические, технико-технологические аспекты, определение норм использования трудовых ресурсов, изучение конкурентоспособности товаров, выпускаемых различными предприятиями, а также организация рациональной реализации своих товаров.*

Ключевые слова: *Предприятие, рынок, потребность, труд, ресурс, норматив, товар, сбыт.*

At the time when the market economy was formed and developed in our country, great importance was attached to satisfying the market needs of various production entities, and to the production of quality products for the world market. Their economic activity is determined only by their competitiveness in the world market, and for this, first of all, it is necessary to know all the laws and rules of marketing and organize it correctly.

Organization of marketing service is a set of material, financial, normative and other resources necessary for the implementation of marketing activities, and in the process of its implementation, it is to direct, organize and coordinate the activities of all employees towards one goal. Economic, technical and other laws are consciously used in this. This activity is a complex system that requires a lot of knowledge, enthusiasm and dedicated work from marketers. Its complexity lies in the fact that it is constantly developing and changing, it is made up of many small systems, specific elements.

The components of the marketing service organization system consist of the following: principles of goals, tasks (functions), organizational structure, methods, techniques and technology of organization, personnel, etc.

The purpose of the marketing organization varies depending on the level of complexity of the system. The criteria and purpose of its organizational structure mean the dynamic stability of the structural structure of marketing, evolutionary changes and interaction with the external environment. It is primarily determined by the goal of marketing. This goal is to manage all activities aimed at achieving a defined level of profit in the areas in which marketing operates. The organization of marketing is fundamentally different in its characteristics from the organization of other areas of the economy. For example, the organizational system of each enterprise, transport organization, communication or service organization is an activity aimed

only at improving its economic activity, obtaining high profits, benefiting its team members, and improving their standard of living.

The purpose of marketing groups, departments and departments is to manage in the interests of the collective of which they are members. However, traditional marketing is an activity that is carried out considering three different interests:

- Due to the fact that they are independent enterprises, first of all, they are a set of works to be performed in order to conduct their activities, to improve economic guidelines, as a result of which they should receive high profits or organize their activities well;
- They serve consumers and should act in their best interests. The consumer's demand, his desire and desire should be the law for marketing and should be fulfilled.
- Marketers must be in constant contact with consumers, their desires are always changing, and they must organize their activities accordingly and, if necessary, change their work methods and methods.

A pure marketing company serves product suppliers, product manufacturers, and sellers, and therefore organizes its business activities in their interests. For this purpose, they study the needs of the producers of the goods, analyze the capacity of the market, its niche, opportunities, collect information about all the market elements, such as the balance of demand and supply, insurance, tax system, etc.

For this purpose, marketing personnel control the development of the need for goods, the in-depth analysis of trends in supply and demand, the creation, design, testing, and introduction of each new product that appears on the market. Its origin, source, buyers and producers should all be studied. These require not only planning of marketing activities, but also the determination of their perspective several years in advance.

This includes all aspects of the enterprise's production, sales, socio-economic, technical and technological aspects. They participate in determining the norms of use of live and generalized labor resources, study the competitiveness of goods produced by various enterprises. They also organize the rational sale of their goods and at the same time solve the issues of material and technical supply: they analyze the economic and technical condition of industry, agriculture and other sectors, participate in determining the prospects of the near and far future. They organize production operationally from the point of view of marketing, organize labor and its remuneration at a high level, etc.

Marketing is very important. Rational organization of the marketing service and precise distribution of its functions among its departments allows effective use of financial, labor and material resources and has a great impact on increasing the competitiveness of the company and increasing production efficiency. A number of requirements are placed on the organization of marketing. One of them is the clear creation of the marketing system, for which the functions must be distributed correctly among the structural units within them, as well as among the various services.

When the marketing service is properly structured, there should be no overlap and parallelism between separate structural units. In the general system, a certain workplace should be allocated for each individual link, and the functions should be clearly established. The absence of this condition will only lead to misunderstandings and irresponsibility for work. In improving the marketing service, the number of instances between the lower and upper links should be reduced as much as possible. As the number of links decreases, marketing issues are

solved more simply and operationally, and the path of documents becomes shorter. Marketing organization is required to simplify the management apparatus as much as possible. It is solved by reducing the number of workers, increasing labor productivity, using computer equipment, modern information technologies.

Simplification and reduction of the personnel apparatus, improvement of marketing development, simplification of the accounting book can be solved by more rational organization of operative work. The marketing apparatus should be flexible and flexible, able to respond quickly to the needs of the times, and able to reflect each new progressive representation. A number of factors influence the structure of marketing services. First of all, the organizational structure of this firm depends on the network of the national economy (or economic region), the volume of production and construction. As the number of consumers who consume goods increases, so does the number of suppliers, and labor costs for receiving and processing incoming materials increase.

In small enterprises, for example, there may not be an independent marketing department, this task may be performed by several people in another department, and on the contrary, in large enterprises (for example, Tashkent Aviation Enterprise and Tashkent Tractor Enterprise), several independent departments deal with marketing issues. The structure of marketing services also depends on the nature of production. In mass flow production, goods are produced, and materials are consumed at a uniform rate and in relatively large quantities. The nomenclature of serially produced goods and consumable material resources increases as they decrease in relative quantity.

Operability, flexibility and adaptability of the organizational structures of marketing services are provided by the regulation of compensation, obligations, rights of individual departments, as well as the long-term marketing strategy of the firm. In the organizational structure of marketing services, it is important to ensure the correct and reverse, "opposite" communication between the functional services of the general management of the company and the marketing services. Generally, the simpler the structure, the fewer the number of coordinating and central management services, the stronger the management system and the higher the probability of success. .

Compliance of the structure in the organizational structure with the specification of the range of manufactured goods and services; compliance of the organizational structure with the size of the sales market return and their characteristics; orientation of the organizational structure of the firm to the deepening of market segmentation, application of a differentiated approach to a particular group of consumers is taken into account. These will help resolve issues. In order to accelerate the sale of goods of such quality and characteristics, services are formed according to the resulting consumer groups. Such an organization of management production departments envisages the creation of services for target markets.

The organizational structure of marketing groups or departments is determined and derived from the location of the company, firm, organization or enterprise, natural conditions and, in general, the regional characteristics of that place. For example, the marketing department of a company located in a large industrial center, in an industrial city, should reflect the cultural background of the place, the needs of the employees, and the character of the majority of its employees.

When organizing marketing, it is necessary to follow the same rules, regardless of how it is structured. Their set is called a principle. The principle is derived from the Latin word "tamoyilium", which means "leader", "idea", the basic principle, that is, the main rule of behavior or activity.

At the current stage of the transition to a market economy, the following principles are followed in the organization of marketing:

- adherence to division of labor;
- obedience to authority, observance of discipline and order;
- unity of command, monopoly and collegiality in management;
- material and moral stimulation of work;
- compliance with centralization and hierarchy;
- permanence, unity and uniformity of workers and employees;
- initiative and fairness (objectivity);
- scientific basis;
- economy and efficiency.

Let's consider each of these principles separately.

The principle of optimal division of labor within marketing organizations is a situation in the organization of marketing. The principle, goal, and purpose of the division of labor in the organization of marketing is to increase the volume and quality of production only with primary costs. As community members grow, multi-tasking departments begin to emerge instead of single-tasking. A worker who always produces a product, a supervisor who always supervises a job, feels a sense of confidence and accuracy, which has a positive effect on the quality of the manufactured product. We know that quality matters in marketing. Its improvement is one of the main achievements for marketing. The division of labor helps reduce the number of objects on which attention and effort must be directed.

The principle of obedience to authority is the right to command and make decisions, and the obedience of all to it. According to the statute, people distinguish authority authority and personal authority in the chief, these things should be embodied in the chief's intelligence, knowledge, experience, and services. The head of the marketing department of the enterprise must have these circumstances, otherwise the department may not justify the trust of the enterprise. Power cannot be understood without responsibility and accountability. Where there is power, there is responsibility. Everyone respects a responsible marketing manager. Such a leader is appreciated everywhere. But they do not like responsibility as much as they like power. A good leader should have a good understanding of his responsibilities. A marketing manager should embody these qualities and characteristics. power, the best guarantee of not abusing the act is the personal pride of the leader, a high human feeling. It is necessary to pay attention to these qualities when choosing or choosing the head of the marketing department. Only then will a positive result be achieved in the organization of marketing.

The principle of discipline and compliance is the behavior of marketing employees and their behavior, outward signs of respect, in accordance with the agreement of the enterprise. Discipline is a necessary factor for any job to be done well. No enterprise, department that you can develop. Marketing is no exception. If there is a lack of discipline between the head of the marketing department and the employees under his command, this deficiency should not be sought from the employees, the fault is due to the negligence of the boss. One of the factors that

have a positive effect on discipline is agreement (agreement). The most basic agreement should be clear and in accordance with the interests of both parties, i.e. the boss and the employees. This is a very difficult issue. If the marketing manager can solve this problem, he can make positive progress in marketing organization and implementation.

Observance of order refers to two types of order: material order and social order.

The rule of material order is as follows: everything has a place, and everything will be in its place. In order to fully achieve the goal, it is necessary to place things well, and the chosen place must facilitate all operations.

The rule of social order is as follows: everyone has a clear place and everyone should be in their place. This rule must be followed in order for social order to be established in the enterprise. The social order again requires that the worker and the place correspond to each other. Social order, for example, requires a clear knowledge of marketing resources and social deficits, and the correct organization and maintenance of the balance between these means that management is very difficult, for example, the larger the volume of work performed by the marketing department of an enterprise, the more difficult it is to manage it. As a result, when this is violated, the common good is sacrificed for the betterment of private interests. As a result, the number of staff will increase, inappropriate personnel may be assigned to responsible jobs, which will lead to the deterioration of the enterprise's performance.

The principle of unity of command is also important in marketing management. If this principle is violated, it will damage the reputation of the authority, for example, the marketing manager, the director, and it will go out of the way of discipline and order will be broken. This has a negative impact on the organization of marketing. According to this principle, when organizing marketing, an employee should follow the orders of only one boss. For example, the manager of the marketing department has an employee attached, that is, the department manager only gives orders to the department employee. The principle of unity in the organization of marketing can be explained as follows: a single boss and a program with a single goal. This is a necessary condition for good work, but it does not negate the collegiality of solving the problems of monopolies. Perhaps it means that issues are resolved collegially and responsibility is assigned to a single person. This implies the subjugation of personal opinions to public opinion. The meaning of this principle is as follows: the interests of marketing group workers in an enterprise should not be prioritized over the interests of the enterprise, the interests of the general public should be higher than the interests of individuals and groups of individuals. If an employee in the marketing department works only for his own benefit, he will be preventing the company from getting a high profit and entering the world market. As a result, the company's failure to achieve good results affects the interests of the employees. Alignment of two categories of interests is one of the main tasks of marketing organization. For this: This implies the subjugation of personal opinions to public opinion. The meaning of this principle is as follows: the interests of marketing group workers in an enterprise should not be prioritized over the interests of the enterprise, the interests of the general public should be higher than the interests of individuals and groups of individuals. If an employee in the marketing department works only for his own benefit, he will be preventing the company from getting a high profit and entering the world market. As a result, the company's failure to achieve good results affects the interests of the employees. Alignment of two categories of interests is one of the main tasks of marketing organization. For this: This implies the subjugation of personal opinions to public

opinion. The meaning of this principle is as follows: the interests of marketing group workers in an enterprise should not be prioritized over the interests of the enterprise, the interests of the general public should be higher than the interests of individuals and groups of individuals. If an employee in the marketing department works only for his own benefit, he will be preventing the company from getting a high profit and entering the world market. As a result, the company's failure to achieve good results affects the interests of the employees. Alignment of two categories of interests is one of the main tasks of marketing organization. For this: should be higher than the interest of the group of individuals. If an employee in the marketing department works only for his own benefit, he will be preventing the company from getting a high profit and entering the world market. As a result, the company's failure to achieve good results affects the interests of the employees. Alignment of two categories of interests is one of the main tasks of marketing organization. For this: should be higher than the interest of the group of individuals. If an employee in the marketing department works only for his own benefit, he will be preventing the company from getting a high profit and entering the world market. As a result, the company's failure to achieve good results affects the interests of the employees. Alignment of two categories of interests is one of the main tasks of marketing organization. For this:

- A good example of a boss.
- Deals as close to reality as possible.
- There should be strict control.

The principle of promotion means material and moral awarding of marketing services, payment for work done. The award should be realistic and marketing should satisfy the employee and the business. The incentive measure depends on the quality of the employee's work, knowledge and the form of payment. The way employees are paid is important for the success of the work. In practice, there are many solutions to this task, but none of them is completely satisfactory. Our task is to develop maximally optimal true types, but this is a very difficult problem. Chin should ensure genuine appreciation, encourage action, and not lead to out-of-bounds disagreements. Solving these issues is the task of us marketers and economists.

The principle of centralization and hierarchy may or may not be accepted by some leaders, but it certainly works in large or small numbers. It is advisable to combine centralized and decentralized methods in the organization and implementation of marketing. Centralized tasks should be managed from the point of view of economic interests of the state and from the point of view of the interests of producers and consumers. Hierarchy requires that there is a line of management from top to bottom in management. Hierarchy "track" is a path through which papers go to higher authorities and from there they come down. But this way is not very fast, sometimes a piece of paper can move the marketing department of an enterprise very slowly.

The principle of constancy (importance) and unity of the composition of employees. If a worker or an employee is replaced before he can learn a new task, it also destroys the opportunity for him to benefit the company. If such changes are made continuously and frequently, the task will never be done well and perfectly. Such mistakes are dangerous for any businesses, because it takes a lot of time to master and learn the whole task there.

The initiative increases employee engagement, which has a positive impact on marketing management. Bosses, workers' initiative is a great strength and is of great importance to the enterprise. It is known mainly in difficult times. A boss who gives initiative to his servants is

superior to a boss who fails to do so. This principle is especially important in marketing activities, because only an enterprising marketer can achieve success.

Authenticity is also an important factor in the implementation of marketing activities. A marketer cannot deceive his customer, the supplier of goods, otherwise he will face a crisis and become discredited. In order for the marketing staff to perform their work thoroughly, faithfully and earnestly, they should be treated fairly and truthfully in their incentives and be friendly. Marketing staff should be consulted when they demand truth and equity. But he should fulfill these requirements without violating any principle, without harming interests in general. For this, the head of the marketing department should use all methods.

The principle of scientific basis of marketing organization is of particular importance. Marketing is carried out taking into account the requirements of objective economic laws. Therefore, the organization of marketing is carried out on the basis of deep scientific research, taking into account all the objective conditions, taking into account the trends in marketing activity, its working mechanism and possibilities. In the implementation of marketing, science implies an individual approach to each issue and mastery of activity against any template. These issues should be considered and resolved on a scientific basis.

The scientific basis of the activities of marketers makes them customers and suppliers of goods into permanent customers, admirers, and allows to establish trust and friendly relations between them.

The principle of efficiency in the organization and implementation of marketing requires solving any marketing issues in a short period of time with low costs. Broadening of efficiency in marketing activities, organization of rational use of resources, reduction of stock of goods, acceleration of circulation of goods, delivering them to the buyer with low costs. This is the main content of this principle.

The basis of this principle is to achieve the correct and optimal structural structure of marketing departments and groups, to ensure the appropriateness of capital spending, and to correctly determine the direction of technical development.

REFERENCES

1. Basovsky LE Marketing: Course lecture. - M.: INFRA-M, 2010. - 219 p.
2. Bronnikova TS Marketing: theory, practice: uchebnoe posobie / TS Bronnikova – 2nd ed., pererab. i dop. - M.: KNORUS, 2010. - 208 p.
3. Gerasimov BI, Mozgov NN Marketingovy issledovaniya rynka: uchebnoe posobie / BI Gerasimov, NN Mozgov. - M.: FORUM, 2009. - 336 p.: il.
4. Paramonova TN Marketing: uchebnoe posobie / TN Paramonova, IN
5. Ibragimov RG Marketing. Darslik, T.: "East", 2002
6. Krasyuk; pod ed. TN Paramonovoy. - M.: KNORUS, 2010. - 190 p.
7. Rozova NK Marketing. - SPb.: Peter, 2008. -176 p.
8. Fattokhov AA, RNKarimova distributor activities in the market. Study guide. - T.: TDIU, 2009.-227b.
9. Yusupov MA, Abdurakhmonova N. Marketing. - T.: Economy, 2007.
10. Kasimova MS, Abduhalilova LT Marketing studies. - T.: TDIU, 2010.-157 p.
11. Kasimova MS, Samadov AN, Ergashkhodzhaeva Sh.J. Economics of commercial enterprises. - T.: TDIU, 2010.163 p.

12. Kalka Regine. Marketing / Regine Kalka, Andrea Messen; (per. s German. MV Lapshinova). – 3rd ed., ster. - M.: SmartBuk, 2010. - 126 p.: il.
13. Karpova SV International marketing for students of the university / SV Karpova. - Rostov n/d: Phoenix, 2010. - 184 p.
14. Karpova SV Praktikum po mejdunarodnomu marketing: uchebnoe posobie / SV Karpova. - M.: KNORUS, 2010. - 200 p.
15. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Problems of Marketing in the System of Higher Education //Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability. – 2022. – T. 13. – C. 71-75.
16. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Development Prospects of Business Subjects in the Republic of Uzbekistan //Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 13-19.
17. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. The Concept of Marketing Policy in Trade and Service Enterprises //Central Asian Journal Of Innovations On Tourism Management And Finance. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 8. – C. 1-5.
18. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Innovative Strategies Of Tourism Development In Uzbekistan //European Journal Of Innovation In Nonformal Education. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 1-4.
19. Musayeva S. A., Usmonova D. I., Usmanov F. S. Problems with Marketing Research in the Furniture Market //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2021.
20. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Ways to expand network marketing and e-commerce in the wholesale of medicines //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876. – 2022. – T. 16. – №. 06. – C. 113-116.
21. Azimovna M. S. et al. Analysis of the main economic and marketing indicators of FE" DAKA-TEX" LLC //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 4-7.
22. Azimovna M. S., Abdurozиковich M. Z. Features of the pharmaceutical market of the Republic of Uzbekistan //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 201-206.
23. Azimovna M. S. THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF THE MARKETING COMPLEX TO INCREASE THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF PRODUCTS //FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 9. – C. 20-23.
24. Azimovna M. S., Shohrukovich U. S. THE ROLE OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN THE FOREIGN TRADE TURNOVER OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN //Barqarorlik Va Yetakchi Tadqiqotlar Onlayn Ilmiy Jurnal. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 6. – C. 110-112.
25. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Optimal principles of assessing the quality of graduates in higher education //Eurasian Scientific Herald. – 2022. – T. 8. – C. 233-238.
26. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. WAYS TO USE MARKETING INFORMATION IN THE PROCESS OF EVALUATING THE ENTERPRISE //World Economics and Finance Bulletin. – 2022. – T. 10. – C. 9-2.

27. **DI Usmonova**, WAYS TO EXPAND NETWORK MARKETING AND E-COMMERCE IN WHOLESale MEDICINES SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 1 ISSUE 5 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337
28. Usmonova DI, WAYS TO DEVELOP ADVERTISING IN THE HOTEL "LEGEND OF SAMARKAND" 2022: Special Issue "Social Sustainability and Innovative Learning Tendencies" ISSN: 2545-0573